

IT EMPLOYEES' EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE: A ROMANIAN CASE STUDY

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Abstract

Emotional intelligence is a complex of self - mastery, motivation, empathy, free thinking, tact (kindness - level) and diplomacy (peakness - level). The study, with the aim of analyzing the emotional intelligence dimensions and factors of IT employees, included the use of multiple test such as Satisfaction diagnostic test based on basic needs, Diagnosis test of motivation to success (T. Ehlers, 2010), Questionnaire for gradient of work - satisfaction (Ticu C., 2004), Cambridge Health Alliance Test (Shaw, G., 2011), EQD Test - Diagnosis of Emotional Intelligence (Wood, R., 2003). The results highlighted that the higher the EQ, the more obvious the tendency to be satisfied with the work it performs, and the reward it receives for the work done (material or moral rewards) and the interpersonal climate in which they work. ($R = 0.590$, $p = 0.01$), so the health, vivacity, effort capacity is higher in those with high EQ.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, IT employees, Cambridge Health Alliance test, EQD test, emotional skills

1. Introduction

Studies on emotional intelligence have been divided into three directions:

1. Inference makes possible the difference in perceiving the orthoform of their emotions, their expression and regulation, irrigated by empathy. Also, the intellectual development of a person depends, to a consistent degree, on its emotional state. (Mayer & Salovey & Caruso, pg 19)

2. The components of emotional intelligence are allied to the observable behaviors that can be adjusted in the educational process - intrapersonal, interpersonal, adaptive, stress - control, syn - mood (Reuven, B., p. 102)

3. The level of emotional intelligence imbues the series of constructs that make up it and which could be called character traits of the human being <<< self-consciousness, self-control, motivation, empathy, social - skills. The concept of emotional intelligence has been defined as a true mix of self - mastery, motivation, empathy, free - thinking, dignity. These attributes of the person make her have a high emotional intelligence. Thus, she can control her emotional responses with others because she is aware of all the factors that contribute to the reaction. (Goleman, D., p. 199).

2. Research aims

We aim to identify, in a legitimate way, the role of emotional intelligence in the professional success of IT workers. We have overlooked the fact that professional success resides in a direct relationship with the level of emotional intelligence, so that people with an elevated EQ are characterized by greater motivation for success, work - satisfaction, a higher degree of satisfaction of the

foundation needs and increased activism (job & wage - success). The experimental study was conducted for a group of 35 employees (F = 23, M = 12), of which 4 = heads of departments, 11 = heads of departments, 10 = office - heads and 10 = trainees.

3. Methodology

1. Satisfaction diagnostic test based on basic needs

This test balances the satisfaction of the following needs: material, safety, social, recognition and respect, self-reliance and self-disclosure. It consists of 15 needs to be paired by comparing pairs. The ranks are entered in the special form. Calculate by the number of X each statement, then calculate the values for the pentagon - the 5 basal needs, according to the specific matrix, SDBN, to determine, by reference to the following grid, the reference values: 0 - 13 = full satisfaction, 13 - 16 = partial satisfaction, 26 - 35 = total satisfaction

2. Diagnosis test of motivation to success (T. Ehlers, 2010)

It contains 41 statements that are appreciated by DA or NO. Respondents are traumatized in relation to the extent to which their claim is true. The results are processed according to the test key, MSD and totals, and then the specific gradient is analyzed: 1 - 10 = motivation to low success, 11 - 16 = average level of motivation to success, 17 - 20 = moderate level, > 21 = level too high.

3. Questionnaire for gradient of work - satisfaction (Ticu C., 2004)

It contains 32 statements that are ascended and appreciated on the actual scale, WSG, from 1 to 6, as follows: 1. never true, 2. very rarely true, 3. sometimes true, 4. often true. 5. very often true, 6. always true

The questionnaire identifies the following factors:

- *remuneration and promotion* - employee dissatisfaction (low - scores) or employee satisfaction (high - scores) with regard to reward for their work (pay, other financial rewards, recognition of merits, promotion possibilities)
- *leadership and interpersonal relationships* - Employee dissatisfaction (low scores) or employee satisfaction (high scores) regarding the social climate and working relationships both in terms of relationships with colleagues or with the boss, as well as under the nonconflict atmosphere.
- *pedantation and communication* - employee satisfaction (low scores) or employee satisfaction (high - scores) on how work is organized and accomplished e.g. task - definition, effort, communication, mazeback, feedback, etc.
- general satisfaction - the extent to which the employee is satisfied with the work he is doing and with the rewards he receives for the work done (material or moral rewards) and the interpersonal climate in which he carries out his work.

4. *Cambridge Health Alliance test * CHA (Shaw, G., 2011)*

It is appropriate for the determination of the state, the cenesteic dynamics, activism and mood. The respondent is requested to report his / her moment status to the column of indicators, recruited to be appreciated in the range 1 - 7, on the vectorial criterion: holo - state = this factor reflects health, fatigue, strength, vitality; activism = reflects the mobility, speed and promptness of reactions / functions; mood = reflects the attributes of emotional state. The mean values of these factors are 5 - 5.4.

5. EQD Test - Diagnosis of Emotional Intelligence (Wood, R., 2003)

The instrument analyzes: self - regulation - the ability to direct and control their own emotional state; self - awareness - the degree of knowledge and understanding of one's own feelings; empathy - identifying and decrypting the feelings of others; social - skills e.g., the ability to establish and influence relationships with others. The test contains 6 situations with 3 responses each for the four components. Respondents are asked to choose only one answer from options A, B, C. At the end of the test is the key that allows you to calculate the points for the answers. After that, the architecture of emotional intelligence, including the distribution of strengths and vulnerabilities, is determined. The results of the emotional intelligence test were obtained by aggregating the points accumulated in the intelligence - puzzle. According to the author's instructions, the number of choices corresponding to the high level of the EQ, the average and the low level are calculated. Carrying subjects on levels in strict and explicit dependence on EQ: High EQ 62.80%, Average EQ 22.90%, Low EQ 14.30%. The individual scores (*avanapex*) on this scale vary within the limits 3 and 17. This interaction shows the interapex and finally (*apex*) is reached - the maximum value = 24. We distribute the frequency of the answers by groups (low frequency = 1 - 8 choices, medium frequency = 9 - 16 elections & elevated frequency = 17 - 24 elections).

4. Results

EQ tests

Even if 62.8% of the subjects prevailed in the corresponding EQ responses, however, most subjects (82.9%) opted for the 9 - 16 scale for the responses indicating the high EQ and the number of those who had high scores

for this variable is only 5.7%. There is also a high number of subjects who made few choices that target the average EQ (77.4%) and low EQ (85.7%). The data obtained in this test allows us to see that most IT staff have the ability to direct and control their own emotional state, understand their own feelings, identify and decipher the feelings of others, and establish relationships with entourage and influence it. The theoretical research of the given theme allowed us to identify the main components of success focused on information technology. For each item, the specific IQD technique was administered. The results were analyzed in logical and transparent correspondence with these obvious components.

Diagnosis test of the degree of satisfaction

Most of the employees in the IT profile export the state of total dissatisfaction to the basic needs, the most frequently frustrated being the need for anchoring on reverence (88.6%), then the material ones (82.9%), after which - isovalently - security and social needs (74.3% each). Fewer are the subjects who have emancipated the frustrated frustration of the need for self - reliance.

The prism of basic needs satisfaction encompasses 22.9% of employees with an anchor perception of self-realization and pleased with the nature of social relationships. 1/5 feel safe, 8.6% are fully satisfied with material, living conditions, and only 2.9% believe that they are recognized in plenary, merits and at the same time are aware and recognize that they are valued, respected.

Leveling WSG questionnaire results

In terms of remuneration and promotion, 22.9% of employees are satisfied with the reward for their work (wages, other financial rewards, recognition of merits, promotion possibilities) and ¼ of the study participants are fully satisfied

with salary. The social climate and working relationships are dissatisfied with 40% and only 14.3% feel satisfaction both in terms of relationships with colleagues or with the boss, as well as under the nonconflict atmosphere. ¼ of respondents are not satisfied with organization and communication. 22.9% are satisfied with the way the work is organized and done, ie the way the tasks are done, the effort, the communication, the feedback, etc. The majority (74.3%) are partially satisfied with work, 11.4% are not satisfied with the work they are doing, and with the rewards generated by the work done. Only 14.3% of IT workers are content with material and moral rewards, as well as with the interpersonal climate in which they work.

Level distribution of CHA questionnaire results

Low status indicators have reached 60%, ie they feel a fatigue, health - problems, lack of vitality. Only 1/5 of the employees have the high score, namely this batch is energetic, potent, healthy. 65.7% of the activism variable has a low - rate of reactions / functions and only 14.3% is characterized by mobility, celerity and promptness of reactions and functions. The dummy provision covers 62.9% and only 1/5% considers the predominantly positive emotional background.

Results of the diagnosis of motivation to success

We find that there are inexistent subjects that would have a lack of motivation towards success, and yet only 48.6% of them have moderate motivation towards success, considered by the test to be advertised / optimal for the activity, because it allows the assumption of risks within the rational limit. The other 51.4% export motivation to excessively high success, which can cause them to take risks without support or avoid some situations out of fear of failing.

The aim pursued / spied in SMD research is to scan the role of emotional intelligence in the professional success of IT workers.

Table 1

Correlations between first set of EQ variables

	MIR	WHS	DPS	APS	PSG	SN	RN	ASR	SM
PHG	EQB								
R	0,445	0,445	0,590	0,425	0,587	-	-	-	0,445
P	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,627	0,615	0,632	0,01

Table 2

Correlations between the second set of EQ variables

	MIR	WHS	DPS	APS	PSG	SN	RN	ASR	SM
PHG	EQS								
r	-	-	-	-	-	0,766	0,710	0,740	-
p	0,663	0,663	0,744	0,621	0,738	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,663

The correlations between the following variables were obtained through endogating / endoporting: "High EQ" with "Average EQ" ($r = -0.615$, $p = 0.01$); "Low EQ" ($r = -0.663$, $p = 0.01$). This shows that how much the frequency of the score increases, as well as the situations in which IT employees show an elevated capacity to solve emotional problems (by mastering their own emotional state, understanding inner feelings and others, so as to relate them) with others in a

pleasant, mature and preventive way) and the fewer are the situations in which they are unable to cope with relational situations. The "high EQ" correlates directly proportional to management and interpersonal relations ($r = 0.445$, $p = 0.01$), so employees with EQ are more satisfied with the social climate and labor relations both in terms of relations with colleagues or their boss, as well as that of the distinctive, nonconflictual atmosphere. The "big EQ" with overall work satisfaction ($r = 0.445$, $p = 0.01$), the higher the EQ, the more obvious the tendency to be satisfied with the work it performs, and the reward it receives for the work done (material or moral rewards) and the interpersonal climate in which they work. ($R = 0.590$, $p = 0.01$), so the health, vivacity, effort capacity is higher in those with high EQ.

- "High EQ" correlates with activism ($r = 0.425$, $p = 0.01$), meaning people with higher EQ tend to be more energetic, active, able to react promptly to situations.

- "Big EQ" with mood ($r = 0.587$, $p = 0.01$), emotional wallpaper is more positive for employees with high EQ

- "High EQ" correlates in response to security needs ($r = -0.627$, $p = 0.01$), or the higher the value of EQ, the greater the satisfaction level of the safety requirement

- "High EQ " correlates inversely with the need for reverence ($r = -0.615$, $p = 0.01$), therefore, people who have a higher EQ

- "Big EQ" correlates inversely with the need for self-reliance ($r = -0.632$, $p = 0.01$), people with higher EQ are more satisfied.

- "Big EQ" correlates with motivation to success ($r = 0.445$, $p = 0.01$), the tendency towards success being more evident in people with higher EQ.

4. Conclusions

The relationship between emotional intelligence and atavic - intelligence is established on the basis of emergence, the stringency of which is decisive for any person.

EQ controls the customs of success where IQ is, by its nature and in this sense, in a complaisance and defining - transit. Experience is, therefore, gained on the going, the clearest way to check or lose balance. That's why the success in life claims IQ, but, as you can see, it does not diminish, from start and finally, to EQ. This is the unmistakable proof that beyond the imperative, the argument, the hallmarks of the IQ for integration, inclusion, the true person knows that adapting to their own maladjustment, paves the way or avenue for the world around them on the basis of EQ.

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